

COGNITISM CONCEPT IN LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT

The concept of cognitivism in linguistics is discussed.

"Cognitism concept in linguistics" is a concept in cognitive psychology that focuses on the study of language acquisition and processing. This theory suggests that language is not just a result of habit or conditioning, but rather a complex cognitive process that involves the interaction of multiple mental processes such as memory, attention, and problem-solving skills. It emphasizes the importance of understanding how the brain processes and interprets language in order to improve communication and learning.

One key aspect of "Cognitism concept in linguistics" is the idea that language development is a dynamic and complex process that involves both internal mental processes and external environmental factors. This means that language learning is not just a matter of repeating words and phrases, but also involves understanding the underlying rules and structures of language. By studying how the brain processes and stores linguistic information, researchers can gain insights into how language is acquired and used in different contexts. Overall, "The concept of cognitivism in linguistics" provides a valuable framework for understanding the intricate processes involved in language acquisition and comprehension. By applying cognitive psychology principles to the study of language, researchers can gain a deeper understanding of how the brain processes and interprets linguistic information. This not only helps improve our understanding of language learning and communication, but also has practical applications in fields such as education, speech therapy, and artificial intelligence.

In the field of psychology, cognitive psychology is a widely studied area that focuses on understanding how people perceive, think, and problem-solve. Within this field, the concept of cognitiveism refers to the belief that mental processes such as perception, memory, and reasoning play a central role in shaping human behavior. In the context of cognitiveism, the concept of cognitive learning theory in linguistics, or cognitive learning theory, emphasizes the importance of understanding how individuals acquire, process, and store information. In linguistics, the concept of cognitivism posits that learning is an active process that involves the organization and manipulation of information within the mind. This theory highlights the role of cognitive processes such as attention, perception, memory, and problem-solving in

shaping how individuals learn and understand new concepts. By understanding the underlying cognitive processes that influence learning, educators can design instructional strategies that are tailored to the way learners perceive and interpret information. Moreover, the concept of cognitivism in linguistics also emphasizes the importance of metacognition, or the ability to reflect on and regulate one's own thinking processes. By promoting metacognitive awareness, learners can become more strategic and effective in their learning processes. This aspect of cognitive learning theory highlights the importance of teaching students not only what to think, but also how to think critically and evaluate their own understanding of the material. Ultimately, the concept of cognitivism in linguistics offers valuable insights into how individuals learn, process, and retain information, leading to more effective educational practices and enhanced learning outcomes.

This concept, also known as "cognitivism in linguistics" or cognitive psychology, is concerned with the study of the processes by which people learn, understand, and perceive their opinions, perceptions, and preferences. This concept was developed by American cognitive psychologists in the 60s of the 20th century and aimed to apply the facilities of cognitive self-problem solving to this field. At the same time, cognitive psychology also studies the evolving processes of learning and memorizing things that are changing. This concept is also widely used in linguistics. For example, in the process of learning a new language, people develop themselves by establishing relevant information and giving them the right advice. It is for this reason that cognitive psychology is important for linguistics, textbooks, and teachers. Students learning through this understanding will master issues they may not have mastered completely and have developing methodologies that reinforce their thinking.

In linguistics, the concept of cognitivism specifically affects the practice and acceptability of lawyers, defense attorneys, and advocates. People's use of cognitive applications for learning creates opportunities for them to realize and strengthen their knowledge. At the same time, this concept is also popular in the field of linguistics, and it makes people active as a tool that strengthens and illuminates the information they are learning.

Cognitive linguistics is an interdisciplinary branch of linguistics, combining knowledge and research from cognitive science, cognitive psychology, neuropsychology and linguistics. Models and theoretical accounts of cognitive linguistics are considered as psychologically real, and research in cognitive linguistics aims to help understand cognition general and is seen as a road into the human mind. One of the approaches to cognitive linguistics is called Cognitive Linguistics, with capital initials, but it is also often spelled cognitive linguistics with all lowercase letters.^[15] This movement saw its beginning in early 1980s when George Lakoff's metaphor theory was united with Ronald Langacker's cognitive grammar, with subsequent models of construction grammar following from various authors. The union entails two different approaches to linguistic and cultural evolution: that of the conceptual metaphor, and the construction. Cognitive Linguistics defines itself in opposition to generative grammar, arguing that language functions in the brain according to general cognitive principles.^[16] Lakoff's and Langacker's ideas are applied across sciences. In addition to linguistics and translation theory, Cognitive Linguistics is influential in literary studies, education, sociology, musicology, computer science and theology.

There has been scientific and terminological controversy around the label "cognitive linguistics"; there is no consensus on what specifically is meant with the term.

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